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The Military and Electoral Security in Nigeria: A Comparative Study of the 2015 and 2019 Presidential Elections

Iloanya, Donatus N.

Department of Political Science

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Elections, worldwide has come to be seen as a popular instrument for selecting public and political office holders through voting. Electoral security is an indispensable integral part of the electoral process. Its importance cannot be over-emphasized in order to achieve a free, fair and credible electoral process. The military was invited to come and assist the police in order to have a hitch-free electoral process. But after the elections, there were accusation against some military personnel and some of these infractions include partisan, interference in the electoral process and others. The study used documentary method of data collection and used content analysis with a particular use of document analysis. The sub-headings includes the military Rule in Nigeria, legal framework for 2015 and 2019 presidential elections. Role of the Nigeria military, the military and 2015 presidential elections and the 2015 and 2019 presidential elections. The study found out that the outcome of the 2015 presidential election was generally accepted but the outcome of the 2019 presidential election was rejected by the opposition political parties. The study advocates that the military should be given a defined role when deployed to election duties.

Keywords: Military, Electoral Security, Nigeria: Presidential Elections

INTRODUCTION

Election, Worldwide has come to be seen as a popular and vital instrument for selecting public and political office holders through voting. Indeed, it is regarded as a vital political right of expression of choice of leaders by the generality of the electorates where democracy thrives. In fact, a functional democracy renews itself through credible elections. In all democratic societies, the conduct of elections is regarded as the most appropriate way of establishing the necessary link between the leaders and the led. As stated in political theory, the legitimate power of a government is sourced solely from the consent of the electorate (Sergent, 1984). However, the mechanism and process through which the consent of the electorates are sought and derived is through regular conduct of elections. To this end, an election by universal adult suffrage is seen as the major expression of democracy.

Events and happenings from developed democracies around the world have shown that the importance of election security to the credibility of elections cannot be overemphasized as the conduct and administration of free, fair and credible elections to a great extent depends on the security. Hence, the development and employment of various security measures by various governments and electoral commissions to guarantee election credibility and consequently prevent legitimacy crisis. Sean Dunne (2001), commenting on the significance of election security, avers that reliable security during an electoral process is pivotal to enhancing participants confidence and commitment to an election. He inter alia argued further that security remains an inseparable part of the electoral process.

A panoramic view of the Nigerian electoral process reveals that, since independence in 1960, Nigeria has conducted eleven general elections. The first was the 1964/65 elections during which Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa was elected Prime Minister. The 1979 election, when Alhaji Shehu Shagari was elected President, the 1983 general election when Shagari was re-elected, the 1991/93 election which were later annulled, the 1999 when Chief Obasanjo was elected President, 2003 election during which Obasanjo was re-elected, 2007 election during which Umar Musa Yar'Adua was elected, the 2011 elections which produced President Goodluck Jonathan, the 2015 general election that heralded the emergence of President Muhammadu Buhari and the 2019 general election to which President Muhammadu Buhari was re-elected. Then, the recently conducted 2023 general election that brought the emergence of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu.

In all these elections, only the 1979, 1993 (though later annulled) and the 1999 have been considered by observers as getting close to credible elections. Agber in Ityokaa and Hongor (eds) (2007:137) explained that the reason for their little success was that the regimes that conducted these elections were retiring military regimes and so did not present candidates for the elections. He argues that since the regimes had no over vested interest in the elections, they did not interfere with the verdict of the electorates. For instance, in the 1979 election, the military government led by General Olusegun Obasanjo was retiring from political leadership and he did not present candidates for the elections. Also, in 1999, General Abubakar had no vested interest in the elections and did not manipulate the conduct and results of the elections.

The General elections of 1964/65, 1983, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023 were conducted by the politicians themselves. Consequently, their desire to either retain themselves in power or to install their candidates made them carry out several electoral misdeeds including falsification of results, harassment of electorates at polling stations, transfer of some candidates votes to others, theft of ballot boxes, etc. the report of the conference of Nigeria Political Parties (CNPP) on the electoral process in Nigeria captures this thus:

The electoral process is full of premeditated hijacking and diversion of election materials, the use of security agents, the army, air-force, intimidation, arrest, detention and even killing opposition members, all in an attempt to continue in office ... (CNPP Report 3, 2003:4).

The above scenario is not far from what happened in the 2015 and 2019 general elections. To ensure a hitch-free polls, the Nigerian military and police with other security agencies reiterated their joint commitment to the peaceful conduct of the presidential election. They warned those planning to truncate the process to bury the thoughts.

The involvement of the military was the crux of the matter. The military was invited to come and assist the police in order to have a hitch-free, secure and serene environment for the electorates to come and exercise their civic duty of voting. But after the elections, there were accusations from various quarters across the country against some military personnel. Some of these accusations include: partisan, interference in the electoral process, not being neutral, partial and not conducting themselves professionally, falsification of election results, chasing away accredited political party agents, election monitors, newsmen, selective screening of voters, not taking directives from INEC officials, they sought to disrupt and indeed disrupted the electoral process in some states, (Enabo, 2019).

In a situation where soldiers scared away voters or disrupted the collation process or outright killing of oppositions supporters and agents or carting away ballot materials and worst still giving cover to the ruling party's thugs to steal ballot boxes, result sheets among other untoward actions, the credibility of such election is damaged (Ebonugwo & Kumolu, 2019).

The militarization of the election to the extent of carrying collation centres to a military location and denying international observers access, is clearly unacceptable and a breach of democratic norms, (Obi, 2019).

Military Rule in Nigeria

The question of the overall impact of military rule on Nigeria's socio-economic and political development is very important given that the military as at 1999 had ruled for about 30 years. Military rule has therefore being longer and continuous (1966-1979; 1983-1999) and therefore is a central factor in the nations parlous and pariah state and regressive development and economic growth as at 1999.

A major plank of assessing the military's contribution is by placing their achievements against their declarations and pronouncements at the moments of military take overs and their statements of intentions and objectives.

Military intervention was often presented as interim and temporary efforts to clean, sanitize, reorient, reorder and reorganize the polity, put the nation on the path of solid progress and then hand over power to civil authorities and return to the barracks. It was never intended to become permanent features of the polity as the two prolonged period of military rule and uncompleted transition of Gowon and Abacha. These were more of manifestations of greed and the lust for power and wealth.

Military interventions were meant to curb crisis, disturbances, breakdown of law and order and insecurity, divisiveness, ethnicity, regionalism, conflicts and violence from the polity and build the nation in terms of cohesion, stability and unity. It was supposedly motivated by the need to eliminate vices, intolerance, indiscipline and lawlessness, abuse of office, immorality and indecency in governance and build a new orientation of discipline, sense of purpose and duty, order and propriety of conduct. Almost all the coup de tats made pronouncements about eliminating and stamping out corruption and building administrations that would be intolerant of corruptions. The regimes promised good governance in terms of instituting efficient public services, social service delivery and infrastructure. There were promises of economic development, economic progress and better management of the economy.

The regime sought to eliminate leadership incompetence, irresponsibility and indecision and promised effective leadership driven by patriotism and sensitivity. Further, the military regimes promised equitable, fair and benefits of statehood to all Nigerians. Finally, the regimes promised to maintain the integrity, honour and pride of Nigeria in the international community.

A critical examination of these objectives and promises clearly show that Nigeria did not make any progress but rather regressed. The military regimes were extremely authoritarian and repressive and sought to subordinate and suppress all voice and social forces. Individual and group rights and freedoms were curtailed and abused. The press was repressed and dissent and opposition were suppressed with as much force of law and might that was available or created. There was insensitivity to the plights of Nigerians and governance was actually for the military officers in power and their friends and primordial groups.

The military turned the Nigerian state into an instrument of ethnics, religious and regional hegemony. Military politics and the deployment of state power was exclusionary favouritist and prebendal. Military rule was ethnicised and regionalized and therefore was divisive. State power was used to deprive some, regard others, and provide unequal access and benefits to those favoured. Development was unequal as those marginalized in the power configuration of the military lost everything. According to the Oputa Panel:

The greed of the military dragged the nation further and further away from the project of nationhood. The result is that by the end of almost thirty years of military rule, Nigeria is far more fragmented than it was in January 1966, when the military first seized power (the Punch 04/01/05 as cited by Olurode 2010:128).

The military regimes were extremely corrupt. Some of the most corrupt rules in Nigeria's history were military rulers. The huge resources that accrued from crude oil sale windfalls were stolen or mismanaged. There was no system of openness, transparency and accountability or any serious checks on resource use as all powers were concentrated in the military Head of States and ruling councils. Some of the military regimes saw state resources and corrupt use as instrument of stability, loyalty and solidarity. The military concentrated so much power, authority and resources in the executive and federal government that Nigeria's age long values and practice of autonomy, decentralization and federalism were effectively destroyed.

The military perverted governance and the polity. A might is right, macho, nihilist and violent culture was institutionalized that promoted not just lawlessness, illegalities, abuse and a callous, insensitive and detached leadership, but constructed a terrain in which connections to the military and persons in authority became a protection for lawlessness and ticket for abuses.

Legal Framework for 2015 and 2019 Presidential Elections

The 2015 and 2019 elections in Nigeria were conducted within the framework of the 1999 constitutions (as amended) and the Electoral Act of 2010 (as amended). In line with the OAU/AU Declaration on Principles Governing Democratic Elections in Africa. The constitution provides for fundamental political and civil rights and freedom for citizens including freedom of assembly, association, and the right to participation. The constitution further provides for the holding of regular elections through direct universal adult suffrage hence adhering to the universal principle that sovereignty belongs to the people who select their leaders and representatives and hold them accountable through the ballot box. According to the legal framework, INEC is the mandated institution to organize and supervise federal and states elections. The constitution provides INEC with guarantees of independence and requires that it maintains impartiality in the discharge of its responsibilities. The constitution also provides for separation of powers of the three arms of government, namely: the Executive, Judiciary and the Legislature. The separation of powers principle in the constitution provides for institutional checks and balances, which is crucial in ensuring undue leverage of the electoral process in Nigeria. Both the 1999 constitution and the 2010 Electoral Act provide for an election dispute management system, which is vested in the Judiciary. This is in line with the OAU/AU principles of democratic elections. Based on its overall assessment of the legal framework for elections in Nigeria, the AUEOM noted that it was largely adequate, as it embodies fundamental elements that form good basis for the conduct of democratic elections. However, a significant gap in the legal framework was its failure to give the right to vote to the millions of Nigerians living in the Diaspora. Given size of its Diaspora population, Nigeria's democratic credentials would be further strengthened if opportunity is given to this significant constituents (AUEOM, 2015).

Roles of the Nigerian Military

The constitutional role of the military is well provided in section 217 of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended 2018). It stipulated that there shall be an armed forces for the federation which shall consist of an army, a navy, an Air force, and such other branches of the armed forces of the federation as may be established by an act of the national assembly.

It further stipulated that the federation shall subject to an act of the national assembly made in that behalf, equip and maintain the armed forces as may be considered adequate and effective for the purpose of:

- a. Defending Nigeria from external aggression.
 - b. Maintaining its territorial integrity and securing its borders from violation on land, sea or air.
 - c. Suppressing insurrection and acting in aid of civil authorities to restore order when called upon to do so by the president, but subject to such conditions as may be prescribed by an act of the national assembly, and
 - d. Performing such other functions as may be prescribed by an Act of the National Assembly.
3. The composition of the officer corps and other ranks of the armed forces of the federation shall reflect the federal character of Nigeria.

The constitutional role of the military is clearly spelled out in the 1999 constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria. The primary role of the military is to defend Nigeria from external aggression. This function is to protect the country from external annihilation of life and properties. Another primary function of the military is maintaining the territorial integrity and securing the borders of Nigeria from violation on land, sea or air.

Nevertheless, the role of the military during elections is also clearly spelled out in section 217 subsection 2c of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended 2018). It stated that the military should take part in suppressing insurrection and acting in aid of civil authorities to restore order when called upon to do so by the president, but subject to such conditions as may be prescribed by an Act of the National Assembly.

The military was called upon by the President Goodluck Jonathan in 2015 to support the police to ensure a free, fair and credible election that will usher in a purposeful government. Also, the military was called upon to assist the police in 2019 by President Muhammadu Buhari to ensure that there will be hitch-free, peaceful and safe environment for the electorates to exercise their civil duty by voting on election day.

The crux of the matter is the nefarious activities of some army personnel during the conduct of elections. Most of the personnel were partisan and not being neutral in carrying out their duties. During elections, the military took part without taking directives from Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) officials.

The role of the military partly caused the rejection of the outcome of the 2019 presidential election as the victory of the ruling party, the All Progressive Congress (APC) was rejected by the opposition party, the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP). This led to the contestation of the election outcome at the Presidential Election Tribunal.

The military are essentially invited to assist the police to calm flashpoint areas during elections. High rate of violence is usually recorded during elections in Nigeria. The military are called to help ensure a free, fair and credible election process but most times they disrupt the electoral process.

Methodology

Generally, there are two different methods of data collection, survey and documentary methods. However, for this study, documentary method was used. Particularly content were identified and extracted from existing publications on the issues relevant to the subject under study. Therefore, the method of analysis adopted in this study is content analysis and the variant that was particularly used was document analysis.

The Military and 2015 Presidential Elections

In sharp contrast to the prevalent practices in many advanced democracies of the world, where security forces play no other role in the electoral process beyond their constitutionally assigned task of maintaining law and order due to their successful annihilation of factors that engender election-related crises, elections in Nigeria and some other countries in West Africa have persistently remained a major cause of worry, violence and insecurity (Hounkpe, 2010). Specifically, in Nigeria all elections conducted from independence era till the period of general elections in 2015 brazenly contravene several provisions of the Nigerian Electoral Acts. This, therefore, is an indication to the fact that elections are potential sources of violence and conflict in Nigeria.

The 2015 general elections, the fifth since the beginning of fourth republic (the republic is the longest one ever in the country) was the most heated and hotly contested general elections in the history of democracy in Nigeria even months before a single vote was cast. There was spate of violent acts that preceded the preparations for and the conduct of 2015 elections, most especially between the two major political parties (the ruling People's Democratic Party- PDP and All Progressive Congress- APC).

Before the 2015 Presidential election., there were election-related concerns that became more intense and exasperated by other existing security challenges such as Boko-haram dastardly acts, bombs attacks and kidnappings, orchestrated armed groups in the country. Another concern was the huge doubt about the capability and capacities of the President Jonathan's government to match its talk with work by effectively mobilizing, coordinating the deployment of security personnel to secure 2015 presidential election.

Eventually, the much anticipated 2015 general elections took place in the midst of myriad security concerns, particularly, the steady rising wave of Boko Haram insurgency in the country. The presidential election was conducted on March 28, the election was perhaps, one of the most bitterly fought in the annals of elections in Nigeria. Indeed, the polls occurred after a controversial six-week postponement following insistence by the National Security Adviser and other security related agencies that the election should be postponed for the newly constituted multinational force to accelerate battle against insurgents in the North-eastern part of the country which has been suffering attacks from terrorist sect, Boko Haram.

In all, the conduct of the military had a positive impact on the entire electoral process, their efforts consequently, prevented electoral violence in many areas and thus facilitated the overall peaceful conduct of elections. Apart from providing security for INEC materials and officials particularly in the midst of security threats, the military and other security agents were able to provide secured atmosphere that enabled Nigerians to throng polling booths to exercise their rights to choose their representative leadership (CDD, 2015). In the final analysis, the elections were hailed by many local and international observers as free and fair, nonetheless, the electoral process was regarded as an

imperfect, but visibly a maturing one. The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) was commended from all quarters for organising the elections in a professional and credible manner particularly under challenging circumstances and also for setting up the Inter-Agency Consultative Committee on Election Security which to a considerable extent helped in achieving relatively orderly and effective administrations of 2015 presidential election.

In line with the extent of serenity that pervaded the entire political landscape in Nigeria during the 2015 presidential election, the Punch Newspapers of April 29, 2015 avers that the general view of the security presence at polling units was positive, unlike other previous elections in Nigeria. According to this newspaper, police were visible in all polling stations and were not obtrusive. The conduct of the military during the elections was generally seen as mature and professional. Indeed. To a considerable extent, a notable departure from the past was noticeable in the conduct of the military during the 2015 presidential election. In fact contrary to expectations of many Nigerians, rivalry common among different security agencies was non-existent unlike before. In its place there was an effective coordination of all security agencies that participated in 2015 presidential election under the group known as Inter-Agency Consultative Committee. The elections throughout the country was devoid of incidents of inter agencies rivalry.

But despite the remarkable and tremendous positive feats attributed to the security agents during 2015 elections in many parts of the country, certain loopholes, irregularities and misconducts were also traced to a segment of some military personnel before, during and after the presidential election. For instance, the centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) report of 29th March, 2015 indicated that there were records of cases of intimidation and harassment of voters by overzealous military personnel in Sokoto State during presidential and National Assembly elections. Worse still, the group (CDD) also reported that voters were equally stopped by the army from taking photos and recording the voting process in the same state (Premium Times, July 29th, 2015).

In the similitude of what happened in Rivers State, the military were also accused of duplicity based on the fact that nobody was brought to justice by the agency despite compelling evidence of underage voting as reported in some national dailies In Kogi and Bauchi States during the 2015 presidential election (This Day 28th July, 2015 – (<http://www.thisdaylive.com/articles>)). Particularly, during the countdown to 2015 presidential election, some of the activities of the military and other security agencies were seen by many people as issue that could aggravate tensions during the polls and consequently undermine the credibility of the elections. Palpable fears were raised in many quarters particularly in Rivers State where the conduct of some army personnel portrayed the agency as one that could be manipulated to serve the interest of the ruling party, PDP.

In addition to this, the actions and pronouncement of the Department of State Security Services (DSS) suggested some degrees of institutional bias in favour of PDP even before the conduct of 2015 presidential election.

Nevertheless, there was no rejection of the outcome of the 2015 presidential election and also, there were no litigations as observed in previous presidential elections; the military conducted themselves professionally before, during and after the election.

The Military and 2019 Presidential Elections.

The 2019 presidential election was initially slated on 16th February but to the chagrin of all, prof. Mahmood Yakubu of Nigeria's electoral body, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) announced, in less than six hours to the opening of polls the postponement of the election to 23rd February. The INEC boss blamed the postponement on "logistics and operational problems". Nigerians went to their polling units to exercise their franchise while INEC officials and security personnel were on their duty posts.

There was huge military deployment in the course of providing security during the 2019 presidential election in Nigeria. The constitutional role of the military is to defend Nigeria against foreign or external aggression, not to defend Nigeria against internal insurrection. Internal security is supposed to be taken care of by the Nigeria police. The military, that is the army, the navy and the air force are established to defend the country against external threats to the sovereignty and security of Nigeria. Anybody who is using the military for any purpose other than to check external threats is committing illegality and illegality at that level is treasonable (Amaechi, 2019).

To ensure a hitch-free polls, the Nigerian military and police with other security agencies reiterated their joint commitment to the peaceful conduct of the presidential election. The military and police worked in synergy to guarantee peaceful and exercise their civic right of voting. Any person or group of persons who attempt to truncate the election will be made to face the wrath of the law irrespective of status.

The military's role in election is contained in section 217 of the 1999 constitution which stipulates that the military can be deployed to "assist the police in maintenance of law and order during elections" (Nwachukwu, 2019).

The deployment of the military during elections is to support the police essentially at flashpoint areas. It is not the primary duty of the military but when deployed for election duties, they took the role of the police who are representing the civil authority in law enforcement.

There was military interference in the electoral process during the conduct of 2019 presidential election in Nigeria. Especially in rivers state, Bayelsa State, Akwa Ibom State Cross River State and other parts of the country. It was a general believe that the military especially the Nigeria Army, has questions to answer with regards to the conduct of soldiers deployed to security duties in parts of the country during the election.

Ebonugwu Kumolu (2019) reported that some overzealous soldiers acted in a manner deemed to have undermined the credibility and sanctity of the election. They were accused of having in a show of brute force invaded INEC collation centres in different parts of the country, chasing away accredited political party agent, election monitors and news men. This was confirmed by Mr Edwin Enabo, INEC head of voter Education and information in Rivers State. According to him, some soldiers allegedly invaded INEC offices at Aba road, Port Harcourt and soon embark on a partisan, selective screening of voters. This claim of forceful interference of soldiers in the electoral process was later corroborated by independent witnesses in the state.

Soldiers were also complicit through their excess in the outbreak of violence that claim many lives during the election as was the case in Rivers State which has become a sad reference point. No fewer than 58 Nigerians were reportedly killed during the election, with Rivers State accounting for 30 of this alarming numbers (Nwankwo 2019).

Specifically and strongly faulted military involvement in the election, especially as it borders on participating soldiers not taking directives from INEC officials. Nigeria went through 13 years of brutal military dictatorship and now, at the point where for the first time since 1999 the army is playing such an incredibly direct role in our elections.

Even when General Abdulsalami Abubakar conducted elections as Head of State in 1999, we did not have the military used in the way it is being used today. This is destroying our democracy, this is not the democracy that we saw when we went to vote in 2015 or in 2011 (Nwankwo, 2019).

This is very dangerous to our democracy. If this country has to survive and this democracy has to survive, then this country must take a stand on what to do about military involvement in elections. If the military is not able to take directives from INEC, the law should be amended to ensure they are immediately removed from involvement in the electoral process.

It is unfortunate that the election was marred with allegations of falsification of result, not using card reader in some parts of the country, the militarization of the whole process that appeared to be what we have not seen before. There were evidence of military presence in most parts of the country.

This brazen interference of the military in 2019 presidential election made the apex Igbo socio-cultural organization, Ohanaeze Ndigbo (2019), call on the federal authorities not to involve Nigerian soldiers in election duties as they have turned into interested parties.

The European Union Observation Mission to Nigeria (EOM) stated that Nigerian soldiers barred them from monitoring elections in Rivers State. The observers made the allegation in their preliminary report released in Abuja. The EOM faulted the election exercise and they were denied access to the collation centers (John, 2019). This consequently resulted in the rejection of the outcome of the 2019 presidential election which led to numerous litigations by the opposition political parties.

The 2015 and 2019 Presidential Election

A comparison of the 2015 and 2019 presidential elections showed that both elections were affected by postponements. The 2015 presidential election was postponed in up to six-weeks due to heightened wave of insecurity in the country. These security challenges such as Boko-Haram dastardly acts,

bombs attacks at strategic places and incessant kidnappings, orchestrated armed robbery and violent clashes between opposing political groups in the country. The 2015 presidential election was finally held on 28th March, while the 2019 presidential election was initially slated on 16th February but was postponed to 23rd February when it was actually conducted. The 2019 postponement was caused by logistic challenges.

Another significant feature of 2019 presidential election was that, it recorded the highest number of presidential candidates in the annals of presidential elections in Nigeria. Over 70 political parties were registered and about seventy-three (73) parties fielded candidates for the Presidential Election. This out-numbered the 2015 presidential candidates.

Due to the rising wave of Boko-Haram insurgency in the country in 2015, the federal government at that time constituted a Multi-National force to accelerate battle against insurgents in the north-eastern part of the country which has been suffering attacks from terrorists sect, Boko-Haram. But in 2019, President Muhammadu Buhari, ordered the security personnels to shoot-at-sight anybody distorting the electoral processes.

In 2015, the conduct of security agents had a positive input on the entire electoral process, their efforts consequently, prevented electoral violence in many areas and thus facilitated the overall peaceful conduct of elections (Olajire, 2019).

But the above will not be said of the 2019 presidential election. The Nigerian Army has questions to answer with regard to the conduct of soldiers deployed to security duties in parts of the country during the election. In a show of brute force, invaded INEC collation centres in different parts of the country, chasing away accredited political party agents, election monitors, newsmen, not taking directives from INEC officials and ad-hoc officials, (Enabo, 2019).

The voter turnout in 2015 is better than that of 2019. The voter turnout in 2015 was 46.8% while in 2019 presidential election, the voter turnout was only 39.09%. In 2015, the elections were hailed by many local and international observers as free and fair. Nonetheless, the electoral process was regarded as an imperfect, but visibly a maturing one. But in 2019, the army barred both local and international observers from collation centres.

Also, in 2015, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) was commended from all quarters for organizing the elections in a professional and credible manner particularly under challenging circumstances but in 2019, the commission was condemned from all quarters as most of the political parties went to Presidential Election Tribunal to contest the outcome of the election. The major opposition party, the People's Democratic Party, (PDP) was at the forefront.

An inter-Agency Consultative Committee on Election Security in 2015, was set up to maintain a safe environment before, during and after election. This they achieved. But in 2019, the military, especially the army, was unleashed on the populace and the electoral process.

To buttress this point, in 2015, the election outcome was generally accepted, even the then incumbent president, President Goodluck Jonathan accepted the election result without hesitation. But the 2019 presidential election result was generally rejected by most political parties due to the deployment of the military in the electoral process.

In 2019, there was high number of inconclusive elections in different parts of the country. Inconclusive elections are noted to occur in areas of stronghold of the opposition political parties. But in 2015, inconclusive elections were not recorded.

Nevertheless, there are areas of similarities in both 2015 and 2019 Presidential Elections; Irregularities such as violence that resulted to voter apathy during the presidential elections, intimidation, rigging and harassment of INEC officials and voters. Also, there were massive protests and demonstrations in parts of the country due to myriad of irregularities during the elections.

CONCLUSION

Electoral security is an indispensable integral part of the electoral process. Its importance cannot be over-emphasized in order to achieve a free, fair and credible electoral process. Its well management builds confidence of the people at all levels of the electoral process which helps to lessen electoral apathy. The police is the main institution responsible for electoral security in Nigeria.

The involvement of the military in the electoral process is the crux of the matter. Ordinarily, the military was invited to come and assist the police in order to have a hitch-free, serene and secure environment for the electorates to come and exercise their civic duty of voting. But after the 2019

presidential elections, there were accusations from various quarters across the country against some military personnel. Some of these infractions include partisan, interference in the electoral process, not being neutral, partial and not conducting themselves professionally, falsification of election results, chasing away accredited political party agents, election monitors, newsmen, selective screening of voters, not taking directives from INEC officials, they sought to disrupt and indeed disrupted the electoral process in some states, (Enabo, 2019).

The military's role in election is contained in section 217 of the 1999 constitution (as amended) which stipulates that the military can be deployed to "assist the police in maintenance of law and order during election" (Nwachukwu, 2019).

This study interrogated the role of the military in the 2015 and 2019 presidential elections. It was found out that the role of the military was commended in the 2015 presidential election while their role in 2019 was nothing to write home about.

Also, it was observed that the 2015 presidential election result was generally accepted while the 2019 presidential election outcome was rejected by most opposition political parties.

Another significant observation was that in 2015 presidential election, there was no inconclusive elections in parts of the country but there was high level of inconclusive elections in 2019. These inconclusive elections are recorded in states deemed stronghold of the opposition political parties.

The local and international Election Observer Missions (EOM) accepted the outcome of the 2015 presidential election but were barred by the military from collation centers in parts of the country in the 2019 presidential election.

This study advocates that the military should be given a defined role when deployed to election duties.

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